

Sustainability is a multi-faceted problem with ecological, economical, and societal aspects. We need a holistic approach to tackle it.

Why sustainability is crucial for Europe's future

By PATRICK BLOUET

Sustainability is a major challenge for society, and the need for it has been made clear by recent events linked to climate change, geopolitical tensions and war. However, sustainability is more than the capacity to maintain our living standards. Any approach to sustainability should consider three important aspects: (i) a systemic approach, (ii) the scalability of the solutions, and (iii) the need to reconcile society, the environment and the economy.

A systemic approach means that any solutions considered must result in improvements for the world as a whole. It is not enough to work on something that delivers local improvements while at the same time making the situation worse at the global level. For instance, developing energy transition solutions that reduce the CO₂ emissions in one place while at the same time increasing emissions due to intense mining for critical materials elsewhere is not a globally sustainable solution.

Linked to this systemic approach is the scalability of the solution; it is important to consider whether a solution can be scaled up. It is good to have local solutions, but ideally these solutions should be able to scale up to national, European or global level. Solutions that, for example, increase the demand for particular minerals far beyond what the planet is able to provide are not globally scalable.

It is also important that all potential solutions are viable in a given economic model. Clearly, our current economic model is not designed to support robust environmental responsibility compatible with planetary limits. New economic models will have to be deployed to align the needs of the human population, environmental limits and a viable economy.

Finally, solutions should also be palatable to the population; for example, lifestyle changes are very hard to sell. Without addressing all these aspects, it is difficult to make a clear assessment of the potential of any given solution to the sustainability issue.

Key insights

- Sustainability solutions should be taken in a global context. As an example, defossilizing European industry should not lead to increased emissions due to mining essential minerals elsewhere.
- Sustainability solutions should be scalable to a global level to have impact. Electric cars are beneficial for CO₂ emissions, but they need such large quantities of rare minerals that we won't be able to transition to 100% electric mobility over the next decade.
- Sustainability solutions should also consider societal and economic constraints. Solutions that require lifestyle changes are hard to sell, as are solutions that lead to a shrinking economy.
- Sustainability solutions must clearly express how long they will last for. In parallel, more durable products and recycling materials should be developed, thereby creating a virtuous circular economy cycle.

Key recommendations

- Always look at solutions from a multi-dimensional point of view, including features, performance and environmental aspects (resource usage, the impact on the climate, the impact on biodiversity, etc.)
- Consider end-of-life management at the very beginning of the design cycle for information and communication technology (ICT) products.
- Extending the lifetime of hardware is very dependent on software. Ensure that software is flexible enough to support a 'second life' for hardware (for example through auto diagnosis, auto testing, and a modular structure).
- Develop design frameworks that integrate full product lifecycle management constraints.
- Develop technologies that reduce the use of raw materials and a recycling process that allows true sustainability with very low environmental impact.
- Adapt the manufacturing processes of semiconductor and electronic systems to allow massive usage of recycled materials and strengthening European sovereignty and enabling a real circular economy.
- Revisit business models such that environmental constraints are no longer seen as a drawback but as a huge opportunity for innovation. Create economic value from extending the lifetime of electronics.
- Set-up a strong European training program to develop skills supporting the repair, reuse and the other topics of the 6R framework supporting electronic lifetime extension.

Defining sustainability

Sustainability is a word that is now used everywhere and is a concern for almost everybody. This is perfectly understandable at a time when the continuity of our society is under threat from environmental pressures, geopolitical tensions, and even a war in Europe.

To understand sustainability, it is important to start from its definition. An internet search returns numerous definitions of sustainability, as illustrated by a few examples below:

The quality of being able to continue over a period of time
<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/sustainability>

Sustainability consists of fulfilling the needs of current generations without compromising the needs of future generations, while ensuring a balance between economic growth, environmental care and social well-being
<https://www.becas-santander.com/en/blog/what-is-sustainability.html>

Sustainability is [the] ability to maintain or support a process over time. Sustainability is often broken into three core concepts: economic, environmental, and social.
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/sustainability.asp>

Development must meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.
<https://ec.europa.eu/environment/sustainable-development/>

What all these definitions have in common is the idea of a process which is capable of lasting over a certain period. However, it is important to note that the timescale is not precisely defined; in fact, sustainability is never associated with a duration (such as 10 years, 100 years, or even eternity). There is sometimes a target date to achieve ‘sustainability’, like 2030 or 2050, but never the idea that the solutions could last forever, or that they could create a long-lasting situation for future generations.

The lack of the time dimension in sustainability creates a situation where we don’t know what we are talking about. Actions taken by industry or government give a false sense of security, as we don’t know how long these solutions will last. This has a perverse impact, as decisions are often taken for short-term beneficial effect with potentially very detrimental consequences in the medium or long term.

It is therefore mandatory to integrate the time dimension in sustainability, clearly indicating the period during which the proposed solution is sustainable. It would help greatly to identify the areas where the greatest efforts are needed.

Overconsumption and biodiversity

To seriously address sustainability, there are two major issues which need to be considered very carefully:

1. Overconsumption of natural resources

This refers either to the overconsumption of finite, non-renewable resources or to renewable resources that are consumed faster than they can regenerate. In both cases, sustainability is limited to the consumption of the initial reserve

of resources. This is the key structuring hypothesis in a finite world.

Many different materials are used in our most popular electronic devices. Moreover, the more advanced the silicon technology used to power these systems, the more new materials are needed to build chips and other elements. Despite the increase in the use of raw materials, the level of recycling is still very low, as shown in Figure 1 from a European Union (EU) survey about critical materials in Europe [1].

In 2021, the amount of waste electronic and electrical equipment (WEEE) worldwide totalled an estimated 57.4 Mt – greater than the weight of the Great Wall of China, Earth’s heaviest artificial object. Of this waste, only a small proportion (less than 20%) is properly documented and recycled. Figure 2 shows that there is a huge potential for urban mining.

2. Massive extermination of biodiversity

Regarding biodiversity, electronics has a negative impact in two main aspects:

- *Extraction of materials:* This is mainly due to activities related to mining and refinement of raw materials. In some cases, the concentration of material in ore is very low (for instance 18 to 24 ppm for rare earth materials which means 1000 tonnes of ore need to be extracted to generate between 18 to 24 kg of noble material). This has consequences of impacting a large ground area to extract all these materials. To make matters worse, very often the refinement processes are very water and energy consuming, and polluting. The concentration of these materials per tonne of electronic waste is much higher, and urban mining takes less

Figure 1: Critical raw materials in Europe (IR = (Import - Export) / (Domestic production + Import - Export) EoL-RIR is the percentage of overall demand that can be satisfied through secondary raw materials)

In the example of Figure 3, it is clear that focusing only on CO₂ emissions could give a very positive view of the situation. But looking at energy consumption in detail, the diagram shows that the situation is deteriorating, with all the consequent negative impacts this has on the environment, beyond net CO₂ emission. The same can be said from carbon extraction systems. They

extract CO₂ from the air, but in the process, they also consume significant amounts of energy.

Solving systemic problems requires aggregated indicators which can give an objective view of the evolution of the situation to ensure that adaptations are always going in the right direction. The most

difficult part of this approach is creating models which are representative enough of the various domains which need to be addressed, and then feeding these models with relevant data.

Scalability of solutions

Even though one solution seldom fits all, it is important to consider the extent

Framework component	Description	Examples
Reliability	This is the first step toward product lifetime extension. The time of programmed obsolescence is over. During the design process reliability must be given the same importance as performance, features, cost, ...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid operating points of systems that are too close to the operational limits of the technologies (power, thermal, ...). • Select a technology with better ageing performance.
Reduce	This is a different approach which consists of doing the same as before with fewer materials, with materials which will be easier to manage in the end-of-life of the product, or with new manufacturing paradigms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make thinner PCB with less epoxy resin and thinner copper tracks. • Use alternative materials to PCB (biodegradable plastics, paper) with bio-sourced conductive inks. • Move from a subtractive to an additive manufacturing process.
Recycle	Given the increasing use of rare materials, recycling is becoming mandatory to improve sustainability, although it should be remembered that this will be only for a limited period as the recycling rate is never 100%. Once again, recycling must be addressed during the design phase in making decisions which will try to reduce as much as possible the number of materials and their quantity, while selecting materials which have the highest potential for reuse.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the collection rate of electronic devices. • Improve the recycling rate of metals. • Increase the reuse of recycled material in industrial processes in the electronics and semiconductor industry. • Reduce the environmental impact of recycling processes.
Repair	This is a very important step in product lifetime extension. Very often a product is thrown away just because a simple broken element cannot be replaced to make the system work again. The ability to repair must be addressed during the complete design process of a product, from the semiconductor up to the external product packaging. It also needs to address the supply chain to ensure the availability of spare parts, as well as the creation of a repair network with the right skills.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design systems that are easy to put together and take apart. • Make spare parts available over a long period. • Allow easy failure diagnostics. • Allow easy retesting/recharacterization. • Develop an adequate network of repairers with the right skills. • Develop a reparability index, as already implemented in France, at European level.
Reuse	This is the next step after repair, meaning that if it is no longer possible to repair a product, at least part of the product could still be repurposed as spare parts for other systems. In these conditions it is important to be able to evaluate the remaining lifetime and health of the recovered parts. As with repairing, a specific reverse supply chain is needed to be able to collect product and provide spare parts in the repair network.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In addition to the properties required for repairing, reuse also needs additional properties linked to modularity.
Refurbish	Refurbishing is the step which allows a second life of a product. This means that a component or subsystem is not good enough to be used in its initial application but can perfectly fit in a new, less demanding one in term of features or performance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All the characteristics already defined for repair and reuse apply for refurbishing. • Make sure that unused functions do not create problems for the remaining ones and are securely isolated. • Allow partial diagnosis, retesting and recharacterization of a system.

Table 1: 6R Framework

to which a solution can scale up without resulting in more disadvantages than benefits. This aspect is very tightly linked to the systemic approach, as the impact of a problem and its solutions must be examined together. Too often, a proposed fix is seized upon as the ultimate solution, while considering its constraints in depth shows this is far to be the case.

To give an example, today, electric mobility is seen as the solution to CO₂ reduction in transportation. This may be true if you only consider CO₂ emissions; overall, electric vehicles generate lower emissions, mainly during the lifetime of the vehicle.

Unfortunately, however, when looking at the need in terms of raw materials to support the massive deployment of electric cars, coupled with the need to support the energy transition and electric mobility at the European level, scale-up is not possible; see Figure 4. In order to satisfy European demand, the pressure on critical materials would be so great that there is a high probability it will not happen; at the very least, it would provoke fierce competition for resources with other parts of the world.

This makes it very clear that European sovereignty is strongly dependent on Europe's capacity for recycling materials and subsystems at a very high rate, while at the same time increasing the use of recycled materials in our industrial processes. It is also important to notice that recycling processes must be designed with a low environmental impact in mind and without creating extra dependencies on other materials or components.

This strategy must be applied to all industrial domains where Europe's dependency on raw materials is very important. It can only be achieved if product end-of-life and recycling processes are defined simultaneously during the design phase of a new product.

Reconcile society, the environment and the economy

Sustainability is always linked to society and the economy. It is extremely difficult to decorelate the environment from

Figure 3: Carbon footprint and electricity consumption [3]

Figure 4: Additional materials needed to support electric mobility and the energy transition in Europe [4]

the economy, which makes the concept of green growth, green economy and, more specifically for Europe, the European Green Deal very challenging.

Analysing the situation using Kaya's Equation or directly from raw data about gross domestic product (GDP) (in 2016 constant dollars) and energy consumption (in million tonnes of oil equivalent, or Mtoe) to evaluate the correlation between GDP and energy consumption, the conclusion is almost always the same: technology and process improvements are always undone by increases in population size and living standards, while worldwide GDP is fully correlated to the amount of energy we consume every year, see Figure 5.

Unfortunately, this pattern has not changed over the past 60 years, which creates a real challenge for the European Green Deal to really decorrelate economic growth from environmental impact while continuing to offer an overall high standard of living to the European population.

To account for the complexity of the situation, some new economic models have been proposed. One of them is "Doughnut economics" invented and promoted by Kate Raworth; see Figure 6. In this model, the three dimensions – society, the environment and the economy – are integrated and trade-offs must be done while simultaneously managing all three. The safe area is the doughnut in green, where everything reaches an equilibrium. Any overshoot beyond the doughnut indicates pressure which is not sustainable for the environment. Any red sector inside the doughnut indicates the potential risk of social instability. The figure shows the 2017 estimation for different parameters [5], and it clearly shows we are already beyond the limits for the environment but also regarding the social stability of our modern society.

Moving from the situation today to this kind of model is not at all easy, as the changes needed are enormous. While the model may be interesting, it is far from clear that the population will accept such a new model.

Perhaps a first step towards such a new way of thinking in the technology realm could be to define first our environmental limitations and then define what could be done within these limits in terms of technology. It is too often the case that a particular technology is developed because

engineers can do it, without considering the overall consequences. Changing the algorithm in our development, taking the limitations of our world as a starting point, could result in developing the things we really need and producing an environmentally acceptable solution to a real problem.

Figure 5: split of CO₂ contribution based on Kaya's equation. Link of energy use and worldwide GDP.

Conclusion

Sustainability is a major issue for Europe and, more generally, at the worldwide level. Better transparency on the period for which a solution is sustainable is needed. Scale-up and a systemic approach must be addressed to allow solutions which could be deployed extensively and deliver global environmental benefits. Nevertheless, there are many opportunities for innovation to extend product lifetime and make devices more compatible with a circular economy and lower environmental impact.

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Figure 6: Doughnut economic values for 2017